

Development Of Inclusive Competence Of Future Logoreads

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Abstract: *This article examines the theory and practice of developing inclusive competence of future speech therapists. At the same time, the concepts of readiness for inclusive education and inclusive competence are defined, and the necessary approaches for the effective implementation of pedagogical activities in the conditions of inclusive education are analyzed.*

Keywords — competence, competence, inclusive education, inclusive competence, special teacher (speech therapist), inclusive readiness, mechanism, individual approach.

INTRODUCTION.

The concept of "comretence" means a set of laws, principles, requirements, rules, duties, tasks and obligations necessary for the owner of a certain profession. Competency is related to the professional and practical activity of a person, and it can be understood as the ability to demonstrate the norms of competency in accordance with the requirements of society, on the basis of creativity, in work experience.

The concepts of "comretency" and "comretency" are close to each other, and they can be distinguished as follows. Comretency has the characteristics of individuality, while comretence acquires generality in relation to a person. The main criterion of competence is determined by the result of effective activity and competitive personnel training[8].

In the framework of com-retention approach in redagogical technologies, together with the terms "Com-retention" and "com-retention", the term "based com-retention" is also widely used. Dependent co-retentions are defined as:

- solving social problems in a specific situation is a certain level of functional literacy understood as the ability to apply universal methods of operation based on certain rules and norms of using knowledge (data, concepts, instructions) obtained from various sources of information [1];

- mentioned that it is considered as a type of educational results that cannot be reduced to a simple sum of information and skills aimed at solving real problems, but is considered as the ability (possibility) to solve complex real problems [5].

- defined the concept of "comretence" as intercultural and intersectoral knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary for adaptation and effective functioning in various professional communities [4];

Taking into account the fact that the digital transformation process currently taking place in the higher education system in our country is aimed at the training of competent specialists, the formation of qualification requirements and DTS of educational fields based on world requirements, in particular, the systematization of professional competence in the studied fields, education based on competence - development of educational programs and plans in accordance with educational requirements, planning and organization of the

educational process, taking into account the continuous and step-by-step formation of professional competences of future teachers, is one of the most important current issues.

60112700-Special editors (logoediting) bachelors who are being trained in editorial higher educational institutions in accordance with the "Classification of the main positions and occupations of employees (HALIKK-2020)", pre-school educational organizations, general education in secondary schools, in specialized educational institutions for children with special educational needs, and in general educational institutions where the inclusive education system has been introduced (preschool educational organizations, schools , boarding schools) as a tutor (assistant editorial employee) to carry out editorial activities in accordance with the established procedure and professional activities such as management of specialized educational institutions, educational institutions with an inclusive education system in accordance with the professional standard of the director will have the right to work in the fields.

The analysis of the requirements of the "Special pedagogy (logoreading)" educational direction of higher education, the "Professional standard of the editor" of special editors in higher education institutions and the analysis of the requirements of the current legal documents regulating the practical activities of the main requirements for future logoreaders allowed to express.

The readiness of future logoreads for an inclusive educational environment includes their professional and psychological preparation. The process of professional training, in turn, includes readiness for information, knowledge of individual differences of children, knowledge of educational technologies, knowledge of the basics of psychology and correctional education, individual characteristics of children, readiness of future teachers to model lessons and use variability in the educational process, various developmental disabilities involve components such as cognition[2].

A special editor (logored) is a special correctional and developmental educational method, capable of using technologies in educational practice, sufficiently mastering the solution of specific problems of persons with speech disorders, in special and inclusive educational conditions. Children with

speech impairments of various categories, their parents, are practitioners who can see social deviations in editors.

Today, the requirements for the personal and professional qualities of future logoreads are changing in the context of the introduction of an inclusive approach to the national education system. The role of logoreads in today's society is one of the most important factors for the success of inclusive education. Therefore, ensure the success of inclusive education is considered as the most important component of it.

Psychological preparation for an inclusive educational environment means emotional acceptance of children with various developmental disorders, readiness to include children with various diseases in educational and educational activities in the classroom, and satisfaction with one's educational activities [7,8].

Currently, in the field of education, the study of problems such as "Inclusive readiness", "mutual cooperation of educational subjects participating in the process of inclusive education" is an urgent issue, which the well-known education scientist V.V. including redagogical and psychological structures, as well as practical experience"[3]. O.A. Kozireva concludes that "characteristics of professional editorial activity are determined, including important professional personal qualities" [6].

In scientific sources and peer-reviewed studies, the correlation between inclusive co-retention of logoreading and inclusive co-retention is observed only by chance. However, we believe that it is necessary to consider these two concepts in relation to each other, because the creation of a modern educational environment, the "universal design" of the educational process, is the preparation for professional activity in changing conditions from the future. Conducting correctional and developmental activities in relation to growth and education requires the formation of redagogical-psychological, inclusive preparation that allows solving the tasks of raising children with special educational needs in an inclusive educational environment. It can be concluded that the inclusive readiness formed in the future logoreads will be the basis for the formation of inclusive comretention.

The structure of inclusive co-retention consists of the special skills of future teachers according to their activities and distinguishes its diagnostic, communicative, didactic, diagnostic, transformational, educational and social aspects. The author's conclusions are based on the idea of the relationship between readiness and retention [1].

If we conclude from the above-mentioned points, the researchers put forward the concepts of "inclusive comretentiveness of future logoeads", "inclusive comretentiveness of future logoeads" and different points of view on their content.

On our part, the inclusive comretention of future teachers, taking into account the various educational needs of students and performing professional functions in the process of inclusive education of future teachers, which ensures the inclusion of a child with special educational needs in the

environment of a general educational institution, It is understood as integral personal education that determines the ability to develop and create conditions for self-development.

In the framework of the research carried out by us, inclusive comretention is a system of knowledge, skills and competencies of future logoreaders who are personally conscious, have entered into subjective experience, have personal meaning, and are used in various types of redagogical activities in solving various professional tasks. we understand the main concepts.

The cognitive component of the future specialist's inclusive co-retention includes cognitive co-retention. Cognitive retention ensures the integrity of ideas about redagogic activity, in addition, it helps to develop and enrich the components of cognitive experience, activates the cognitive activity of a person, solves certain theoretical and practical problems, and perceives information in a timely manner. is described as the ability to process, store and display in the mind.

Cognitive co-retention, which is a part of inclusive co-retention, is the ability to think redagogically based on the system of knowledge and cognitive activity experience necessary for the implementation of inclusive education.

This main content is based on scientific, professional and editorial knowledge and it consists of the following: - editorial-psychological foundations of education and training; innovative integration processes in the field of special education; basics of personality development; the basics of editorial management of students' self-development process, encouraging positive self-awareness in all possible areas of activity; the main characteristics of the interaction between a person with a developmental disability and society; takes into account the anatomical and physiological, age, psychological and individual characteristics of students with various developmental disorders.

To sum up, the relevance of researching the mechanisms of formation of inclusive co-comprehensions of logoreads based on an individual approach is related to the needs of the educational environment and confirmed by a number of regulatory and legal documents. The authors who are engaged in the research of this issue recommend a practice-oriented approach to the future logoreader they pay attention to preparation. This allows not only the formation of a system of knowledge, but also the formation of skills to apply them in the process of solving professional problems.

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